

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D5.3

Data Management Plan 2

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Glossary

AB	Advisory Board
CSO	Civil Society Organisations
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PAR	Participatory Action Research
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and examines the current state of democracy in learning environments across Europe, generating a robust evidence base for the design of a participatory democratic curriculum. Critical ChangeLab develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. At the Critical ChangeLabs, diverse actors from formal and non-formal education and civic organizations work together with youth to rethink European democracy and envision futures that are justice-oriented.

This deliverable is the second version of the Critical ChangeLab Data Management Plan (DMP). The document outlines the overall approach to data management and defines the dataset, standards and metadata, data-sharing and archiving and preservation with regards to FAIR Data Management guidelines (EC, 2016). This second version of this document has been prepared as planned on M12 and it will be updated during the project's lifecycle in accordance with the periodic reporting of the project, and as the research activities evolve to include new data, adjustments in the processes deployed, changes in consortium policies or any other issue regarding the data management of the project.

1 Introduction

1.1 About Critical ChangeLab

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and embraces a transdisciplinary approach combining expertise from Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, as well as Science and Technology.

Specifically, the Critical ChangeLab project develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy fosters learners' transformative agency and strengthens democratic processes in education through collaborations across formal and non-formal education and local actors around global/local challenges relevant for youth. The Model promotes creative and narrative practices to explore the historical roots of local and EU-wide challenges, understanding the value-systems and worldviews underlying distinct types of relations (human-human, human-nature, human-technology). At the Critical ChangeLabs, young people are introduced to approaches such as theatre of the oppressed, transmedia storytelling, as well as speculative and critical design to rethink European democracy and envision democracy futures that are justice-oriented.

Throughout the project lifespan, the Critical ChangeLab project examines the current state of democracy within education institutions developing instruments such as the Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index, identifying youth's perspectives on everyday democracy. As part of the project, a scalable and tailorable model of democratic pedagogy in formal and non-formal learning environments is designed. Critical ChangeLab Model is co-created and implemented with youth and stakeholders and evaluated to provide recommendations for policy and practice. Strategies to sustain the model and its outcomes over time are also produced.

The Critical ChangeLab project uses mixed model research design combining quantitative and in-depth qualitative research on democracy and youth with participatory action research cycles to generate a robust evidence base to support democratic curriculum development using participatory, creative, and critical approaches.

1.2 Deliverable scope

The main aim of the DMP is to describe the management of the research and other data that are collected, analysed and produced within Critical ChangeLab according to the rules and guidelines set by the Horizon Europe programme.

To ensure quality of the data management and to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), the Critical ChangeLab DMP aims to:

- Provide information on the data that will be collected, processed and/or generated in the course of the project.
- Describe the methodology, processes and standards to be applied and followed.
- Describe the handling of research data during and after the end of the project.
- Outline how the data will be curated and preserved (including the period after the end of the project).
- Identify responsibilities among the consortium partners regarding the data management.
- Describe which data and how will be shared/provided for Open Access.

This document is structured as follows:

- *Section 2 – The Critical ChangeLab Data Summary:* defines the purpose of the data collected or generated within the framework of Critical ChangeLab along with a detailed summary of data types and formats, data origins and its expected size. It concludes with an overview of data utility and a list of potential stakeholders that might find the data useful for re-use.
- *Section 3 – FAIR DATA:* describes the methods to be applied to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable in the context of Critical ChangeLab project.
- *Section 4 – Allocation of resources:* outlines all necessary resources for making the project's data FAIR, as well as it defines data management responsibilities.
- *Section 5 – Data security:* presents the data security strategy of Critical ChangeLab.
- *Section 6 – Ethical aspects and other procedures:* presents ethical aspects to be considered within Critical ChangeLab along with the processes applied.
- *Section 7 – Conclusions and next steps:* elucidates the next steps regarding the good and FAIR data management of the project.

The Critical ChangeLab DMP will be updated in accordance with the periodic reporting of the project, as well as a continuous reviewing is foreseen in relation to any significant changes during the project life, such as:

- New data
- Changes in the consortium policies
- Changes in the consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving the project).

1.3 List of changes implemented in the DMP

The changes carried out in this update of data management plan compared to the previous one (D5.2), are highlighted in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Changes implemented in the DMP.

Change implemented	Section of deliverable	Description
New section added	1.3 List of changes implemented in the DMP	Adding a new section to detail the changes carried out to the DMP in this revision
Clarifying open data upload sizes.	Section 3.2 Making data openly accessible	Added clarification of the default file upload size in Zenodo.
Clarifying Work package and Task leader responsibilities	4.2 Data management responsibilities	Included one new paragraphs of text to clarify Work Package and Task leader responsibilities related to data de-identification/anonymization, as well as opening data and data-re-use. Included a reference to annex 1.
Clarifying partner responsibilities	4.2: Data management responsibilities	Included one new sentence to clarify partner responsibilities related to opening its data for re-use
Updating figure 1	4.2: Data management responsibilities	Included a mention of the risk assessment submitted by the project coordinator to the organizations data steward to figure 1.
Updated table numbers throughout the document		

2 Data Summary

2.1 Purpose of data collection or generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

The overall goal of the Critical ChangeLab project is to strengthen democracy in Europe by creating and implementing a flexible model of democratic pedagogy using a bottom-up approach that empowers young people to 'own' everyday democracy and engage in direct action towards justice-oriented transformations. The Model is created following a participatory process with youth, educators, and other stakeholders, using Participatory Action Research (PAR) and participatory evaluation.

The project overall goal is broken down into seven specific objectives:

- Examine the current state of democracy within education institutions and identify youth's perspectives on everyday democracy.
- Design a scalable and tailorable model - Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy- for supporting democratic transformations in formal and non-formal learning environments.
- Co-create and implement the Critical ChangeLab Model in collaboration with stakeholders.
- Evaluate the Critical ChangeLab Model process, impact, and socio-economic cost.
- Sustain the Critical ChangeLab activities beyond the Critical ChangeLab project lifespan.
- Share and exploit the Critical ChangeLab project outputs.
- Create a robust evidence base to support democratic curriculum development.

In this context, several activities are planned to achieve the overall and specific objectives of the project. The successful implementation of these activities requires the collection, processing and/or generation of a variety of data that will facilitate the production of evidence-based results and, therefore, raise the value of the project outcomes. The key activities of Critical ChangeLab that are set to collect, process and/or generate data are the following:

- Assessing education institutions' democracy health (T1.1)
- Understanding and comparing youth perspectives on everyday democracies in challenging contexts (T1.2)

- Development of a conceptual and methodological framework for supporting critical democracy education through creative and narrative practices (T1.3)
- Participatory Action Research (PAR) cycle 1 (T1.4)
- Building a community of practice (T2.1)
- PAR cycle 2 (T2.2)
- PAR cycle 3 (T2.3)
- Development of the Critical ChangeLab Educator's Handbook (T2.4)
- Process evaluation (T3.1)
- Impact evaluation (T3.2)
- Socio-economic evaluation (T3.3)
- Implementation of communication activities (T4.2)
- Community empowerment activities for a sustained take up of methods (T4.3)
- Dissemination activities (T4.5)
- Quality assurance (T5.2)
- External Quality Assurance (T5.5)

For the purposes of the DMP, in the project we distinguish between raw data and processed data. Raw data refers to the collection of information as gathered by the source before Critical ChangeLab team members further process, clean or analyse it. Processed data involves some level of manipulation. In the context of the project, the manipulation of the raw data might consist in the removal of personal identifiers through anonymisation / pseudonymisation techniques, as well cleaning and processing to have the data in a shareable, machine-readable format.

Depending on the level of access, Critical ChangeLab datasets are classified as open or restricted to partners.

The datasets generated In Critical ChangeLab will be stored in different repositories. The use of a specific repository will depend on the type of dataset. For instance, raw data containing personal identifiers may be stored in an individual partner's repository and will not be shared across the consortium. Processed data (anonymised / pseudonymised) might be shared with the consortium partners through the Critical ChangeLab project repository. The list of repositories used in Critical ChangeLab is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Clist of repositories used in Critical ChangeLab

Name of the repository	Description	Type of data stored	Access
Critical ChangeLab project repository in Microsoft O365 SharePoint	Cloud-based service to store, organize, share, and access information. UOULU has agreement with this service and manages access to the repository.	(i) Partners' email communication (ii) Project development documentation (iii) Anonymised, pseudonymised research data	Restricted to Critical ChangeLab consortium partners
Partners' institutional repositories	Consortium partners secure access-controlled, regularly back-upped network drives.	(i) Partners' email communication (ii) Project development documentation	Restricted to individual partners' team members
Alchemer repository	Alchemer ¹ is a GDPR compliant service for online surveys. ISRZ has agreement with Alchemer and manages the data collection procedures through this cloud-based service.	Answers to the Democracy Health Questionnaire	Restricted to ISRZ's team members
Critical ChangeLab website	Critical ChangeLab online site hosted in AE server	(i) Project information and outputs (ii) Analytics	(i) Public (ii) Restricted to AE's team members
Individual Partner websites and the social media groups they are part of	Institutional online sites and accounts in social networks	(i) Project information and outputs (ii) Analytics	(i) Public (ii) Restricted to individual partners communication departments and team members
Academic repositories	The portals of the academic publishers where Critical ChangeLab scientific publications will be published. These include individual partners' academic repositories (Jultika ² , TARA ³ ,	Project research outputs	Public

¹ Further information available at: <https://www.alchemer.com/>

² Open access repository of the University of Oulu. Further information available at: <https://jultika.oulu.fi>

³ Trinity College Dublin's access to Research Archive. Further information available at: <http://www.tara.tcd.ie>

	DABAR ⁴ , Diposit digital ⁵ and external (To Be Defined)		
OpenAIRE ⁶ /Zenodo ⁷	Open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows storage of research papers, datasets, research software, reports, and any other related research outputs.	Project research outputs	Public

The main datasets to be collected within the Critical ChangeLab Work Packages (WPs) as they have been identified to M6 of the project are presented in the following tables:

Table 3: WPI datasets

Name of dataset	Survey data on education institutions' democracy health	code: #1
Relevant activity and WP task	Assessing education institutions' democracy health (T1.1)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Democracy Health Questionnaire (digital version available in the online research platform Alchemer)	
Data elements	Assessment of democracy values and practices at institutional level, structured across various dimensions	
Data type	Quantitative	
Format	Data exported as spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data collection through the implementation of survey targeting formal and non-formal learning institutions.	
Data availability	Open	
Available through	Zenodo, Critical ChangeLab website	
Data storage	ISRZ repository (also in Alchemer), Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Answers will be anonymous, and no personal data will be collected through respondents' answers nor through the digital questionnaire metadata	
Name of dataset	Case studies on youth perspectives on everyday democracy	code: #2
Relevant activity and WP task	Understanding and comparing youth perspectives on everyday democracies in challenging contexts (T1.2)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Focus groups, semi-structured interviews, and observation templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data: age, gender, socio-economic background, education level, location, workplace or links with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) (ii) Perspectives on everyday democracy in challenging contexts for democratic participation	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), image (.jpeg/.raw) and audio (.m4a / .wav) files	

⁴ Croatian repository for digital objects from scientific research. Further information available at: <https://dabar.srce.hr/>

⁵ Digital repository of the University of Barcelona. Further information available at: <https://diposit.ub.edu/dspace/>

⁶ OpenAIRE stands for "Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe"

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/>

Data collection/generation Process	Data collection through the implementation of focus groups, semi-structured interviews and ethnographic accounts	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' institutional repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	The raw data to be collected will be analysed upon pseudonymisation/ anonymisation techniques Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed	
Name of dataset	Secondary research on critical literacies	code: #3
Relevant activity and WP task	Development of a conceptual and methodological framework for supporting critical democracy education through creative and narrative practices (T1.3)	
Data elements	Research publications on critical literacies published in peer-review academic forums	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data collected through systematic literature review on critical literacies	
Data availability	Open	
Available through	Zenodo	
Data storage	Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		
Name of dataset	Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 1)	code: #4
Relevant activity and WP task	PAR cycle 1 (T1.4)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation and reporting templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data: age and gender or youth taking part in the Labs (ii) Contact information of educators and collaborators from schools, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) involved in the Lab activities (iii) Learning activities and outputs generated by the Lab participants	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and image (.jpeg/.raw) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs during PAR cycle 1	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Pseudonymisation/anonymisation techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed/ used in communication and dissemination activities No personally identifiable data of the Critical ChangeLab participants will be shared among the project partners	

	Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed
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Table 4. WP2 datasets

Name of dataset	Data stemming from the community of practice building activities	code: #5
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Building a community of practice (T2.1)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation templates	
Data elements	Personal data: Name, position, and contact information of Critical ChangeLab partners and team members involved in the organization of Critical ChangeLabs	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), and spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data collection through the implementation of the community of practice building activities	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed	
Name of dataset	Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 2)	code: #6
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	PAR cycle 2 (T2.2)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation and reporting templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data: age and gender or youth taking part in the Labs. Sensitive data regarding participants' background (socio-economic aspects, belonging to minority groups) may be also collected from the youth involved in the Labs (ii) contact information of educators and collaborators from schools, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) involved in the Lab activities (iii) Learning activities and outputs generated by the Lab participants	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and image (.jpeg/.raw) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs during PAR cycle 2	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Pseudonymisation/anonymization techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed/ used in communication and dissemination activities	

	<p>No personal data of the Critical ChangeLab participants will be shared among the project partners. Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed</p>	
Name of dataset	Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 3)	code: #7
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	PAR Cycle 3 (T2.3)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation and reporting templates	
Data elements	<p>(i) Personal data: age and gender or youth taking part in the Labs Sensitive data regarding participants' background (socio-economic aspects, belonging to minority groups) may be also collected from the youth involved in the Labs (ii) Contact information of educators and collaborators from schools, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) involved in the Lab activities (iii) Learning activities and outputs generated by the Lab participants</p>	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and image (.jpeg/.raw) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs during PAR cycle 3	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	<p>Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected</p>	
Data storage	<p>Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository</p>	
Additional comments	<p>Pseudonymisation/anonymization techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed/ used in communication and dissemination activities No personally identifiable data of the Critical ChangeLab participants will be shared among the project partners Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed</p>	
Name of dataset	Documentation of ready-to-go activities and strategies to facilitate Critical ChangeLabs	code: #8
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Development of the Critical ChangeLab Educator's Handbook (T2.4)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation templates	
Data elements	Critical ChangeLab learning activities designs and facilitation strategies	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and image (.jpeg/.raw) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data stemming from the implementation of the Critical ChangeLabs and the community of practice building activities.	
Data availability	Open	
Availability through	Zenodo, Critical ChangeLab website	
Data storage	Partners' repositories, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		

Table 5. WP3 datasets

Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLabs process evaluation	code: #9
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Process evaluation (T3.1)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Questionnaires, interviews, focus groups and visual design actions such as mappings, zines and portfolios	
Data elements	Personal data: voice recording of the Critical ChangeLab participants interviewed, and the stakeholders taking part in the focus groups	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), image (.jpeg/.raw), audio (.m4a / .wav) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data stemming from the implementation of process evaluation activities	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Pseudonymisation/anonymization techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed No personally identifiable data of the Critical ChangeLab participants will be shared among the project partners Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed	
Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation	code: #10
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Impact evaluation (T3.2), community-empowerment activities (T4.3)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Questionnaires and interviews	
Data elements	(i) Personal data, demographic information of the participants of Critical ChangeLab community empowerment actions (ii) Documentation of the activities (iii) Recording of interviews with youth taking part in the mentorship programme	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and audio ((.m4a / .wav)) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data stemming from the implementation of the project impact evaluation (T3.2) and community-empowerment activities (T4.3)	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Pseudonymisation/anonymisation techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed Each partner is the data controller of its own data	

	The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed	
Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLab socio-economic evaluation	code: #11
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Socio-economic evaluation (T3.3)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Semi-structured interviews, analysis templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data: name, role and contact of the interviewees (ii) Analysis of the Critical ChangeLabs run by partners during PAR cycle 1, 2 and 3	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), and audio ((.m4a / .wav)) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data stemming from the implementation of Critical ChangeLab WPI and WP2 activities, as well as the socio-economic evaluation of the Critical ChangeLabs	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Raw data: until the end of the Project. Processed data: as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected	
Data storage	Raw data: Partners' repositories Selected and processed data: Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	Pseudonymisation/anonymization techniques will be applied to the raw data collected to be analysed No personally identifiable data of the Critical ChangeLab participants will be shared among the project partners Each partner is the data controller of its own data The need for the storage of the data will be yearly assessed	

Table 6. WP4 datasets

Name of dataset	Social media, website and newsletter statistics	code: #12
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Implementation of communication activities (T4.2)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Analytics embedded in digital media used in Critical ChangeLab communication activities.	
Data elements	Number of followers, number of posts, number of visits, number of newsletter subscribers, number of reports downloads.	
Data type	Quantitative	
Format	Spreadsheet file (.csv/.xlsx)	
Data collection/generation Process	Through: (i) the statistics tool offered by the social media platforms (ii) website analytics deployed to the project website (see Annex 2) (iii) mailworx statistics tool for the email newsletter	
Data availability	Raw data: restricted to partners Selected and processed data: open	
Availability through	Zenodo, Internet Archive ⁸	
Data storage	Ars Electronica repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	For reporting purposes, it is likely that the analysis of the above quantitative data results to qualitative data to be stored in a document file (.docx, .pdf)	

⁸ <https://archive.org/>

Name of dataset	Voices of Youth	code: #13
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Community empowerment activities for a sustained take up of methods (T4.3)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Interviews	
Data elements	Personal data: name, age and video image of Critical ChangeLab community empowerment actions participants.	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), and video (.mp4) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Through interviews to participants involved in youth mentoring actions	
Data availability	Open	
Availability through	Critical ChangeLab website, Ars Electronica Youtube Channel, Zenodo	
Data storage	Ars Electronica repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		
Name of dataset	Data stemming from dissemination events and activities	code: #14
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Dissemination activities (T4.4)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation and reporting templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data and demographic information of the audience attending Critical ChangeLab project dissemination events (ii) Documentation of the events (iii) Information regarding partners' participation in external project events	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), image (.m4a / .wav) and video (.MP4) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Through: (i) several events to be organised within Critical ChangeLab to serve the project's objectives and promote its outcomes (ii) Critical ChangeLab partners' participation in events external to the project	
Data availability	Open	
Availability through	Critical ChangeLab website	
Data storage	Partners' repositories, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	No personally identifiable data collected by the participants to Critical ChangeLab events will be anonymized before the publication	
Name of dataset	Documentation of roundtables and online workshops	code: #15
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Dissemination activities (T4.4)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Roundtable and online workshops documentation templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data and demographic information of participants joining the roundtable and online workshops on policy and technology (ii) Documentation of the sessions	
Data type	Quantitative and qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx), video (.mp4) and audio (.m4a / .wav) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data stemming from the implementation of the roundtable and online workshops	
Data availability	Open	
Availability through	Critical ChangeLab website	
Data storage	EUROALTER repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	

Additional comments	Any personally identifiable data collected by the participants to Critical ChangeLab events will be anonymised before the publication
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Table 7. WP5 datasets

Name of dataset	Data on internal project coordination activities	code: #16
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Overall management & coordination (T5.1)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Reporting templates	
Data elements	Documentation of the meetings and the feedback provided	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Through: (i) meetings' minutes (ii) internal communication	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Up to 2 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		
Name of dataset	Data on Critical ChangeLab KPIs	code: #17
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	Quality assurance (T5.2)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Reporting templates	
Data elements	Data related to the fulfilment of project's KPIs as stated in the GA.	
Data type	Quantitative	
Format	Spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation Process	Data collected through: (i) internal monitoring activities carried out by partners and reported in corresponding deliverables and the interim reviews' technical reports (ii) Regular data collection for the purpose of the Interim Monitoring Report and Final Evaluation Report	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Up to 2 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments	For reporting purposes, it is likely that the analysis of the above quantitative data results to qualitative data to be stored in a document file (.docx, .pdf)	
Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLab Ethics Advisory Board	code: #18
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	External quality assurance (T5.5)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data of the Ethics Advisory Board Members (name, curriculum vitae and contact information) (ii) Documentation of the meetings and the feedback provided	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), and spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation	Through:	

process	(i) meetings' minutes (ii) internal communication	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Up to 2 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	UOULU repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		
Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLab Expert Advisory Board	code: #19
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	External quality assurance (T5.5)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data of the Expert Advisory Board Members (name, position, contact information) (ii) Documentation of the meetings and the feedback provided	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), and spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation process	Through: (i) meetings' minutes (ii) internal communication	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Up to 2 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	UOULU repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		
Name of dataset	Critical ChangeLab Youth Assembly	code: #20
Relevant activity and WP task(s)	External quality assurance (T5.5)	
Data collection instrument(s)	Documentation templates	
Data elements	(i) Personal data of the Youth Assembly Members (name, age and contact information) (ii) Documentation of the meetings and the feedback provided	
Data type	Qualitative	
Format	Text (.docx), and spreadsheet (.csv/.xlsx) files	
Data collection/generation process	Through: (i) meetings' minutes (ii) internal communication	
Data availability	Restricted to partners	
Retention time	Up to 2 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	UOULU repository, Critical ChangeLab repository	
Additional comments		

2.2 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

Within the context of Critical ChangeLab activities new data are expected to be collected and generated as well as pre-existing data are planned to be used.

The new data will stem mainly from Critical ChangeLab research and innovation activities and will be provided to the consortium partners by the stakeholders involved in the project activities. Critical ChangeLab key stakeholder groups include:

- **Researchers and research institutions:** individuals and institutions generating knowledge on the project's key areas ranging from youth participation, democracy education and citizenship education.
- **Formal and non-formal education professionals:** teachers, facilitators, guides, pedagogical coordinators as well as directors and managers operating in both formal and non-formal learning environments within Europe.
- **Young people, their families and the general public:** youth aged 11 to 18, but also school-aged children and young adults. This stakeholder group also includes young people's close networks (referring to their immediate family members and peers), and the broader public.
- **CSOs and industry:** non-profits, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and private corporations interested in supporting youth engagement, democracy and citizenship education.
- **Policy and decision makers:** policy and institutional decision-makers across a range of areas but predominantly those who engage with policy surrounding education, democratic participation, and young people.

The pre-existing data to be harvested or generated and utilised during the project's implementation include mainly data collected through literature review and desk-research.

Table 8. Critical ChangeLab datasets

Name of the dataset	Dataset code	Origin
Survey data on education institutions' democracy health	#1	Formal and non-formal education professionals (directors and school principals)
Case studies on youth perspectives on everyday democracy	#2	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations
Secondary research on critical literacies	#3	Researchers' published papers
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 1)	#4	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations and industry
Data stemming from the community of practice building activities	#5	(ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 2)	#6	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations and industry

Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 3)	#7	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations and industry
Documentation of ready-to-go activities and strategies to facilitate Critical ChangeLabs	#8	(i) Formal and non-formal education professionals (ii) Civil society organisations and industry
Critical ChangeLabs process evaluation	#9	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations and industry
Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation	#10	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals
Critical ChangeLab socio-economic evaluation	#11	(i) Young people (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) Civil society organisations and industry (iv) Policy and decision-makers
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	#12	(i) All Critical ChangeLab stakeholders (ii) General public
Voices of Youth	#13	Young people
Data stemming from dissemination events and activities	#14	(i) All Critical ChangeLab stakeholders (ii) General public
Documentation of roundtables and online workshops	#15	(i) Researchers and Research institutions (ii) Formal and non-formal education professionals (iii) CSOs and industry (iv) Policy and decision-makers
Data on internal project coordination activities	#16	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners
Data on Critical ChangeLab KPIs	#17	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners
Critical ChangeLab Ethics Advisory Board	#18	Researchers and Research institutions
Critical ChangeLab Expert Advisory Board	#19	(i) and Research institutions (ii) CSOs and industry
Critical ChangeLab Youth Assembly	#20	Young people

2.3 Expected size of the data

Table 9. Expected size of Critical ChangeLab datasets

Name of the dataset	Dataset code	Expected size
Survey data on education institutions' democracy health	#1	Less than 1GB
Case studies on youth perspectives on everyday democracy	#2	Up to 5 GB
Secondary research on critical literacies	#3	Less than 1 GB
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 1)	#4	Up to 10 GB
Data stemming from the community of practice building activities	#5	Less than 1 GB
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 2)	#6	Up to 10 GB
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 3)	#7	Up to 10 GB
Documentation of ready-to-go activities and strategies to facilitate Critical ChangeLabs	#8	Up to 5 GB
Critical ChangeLabs process evaluation	#9	Up to 1 GB
Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation	#10	Up to 1 GB
Critical ChangeLab socio-economic evaluation	#11	Up to 1 GB
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	#12	Less than 1 GB
Voices of Youth	#13	Up to 20GB
Data stemming from dissemination events and activities	#14	Up to 20 GB
Documentation of roundtables and online workshops	#15	Less than 1 GB
Data on internal project coordination activities	#16	Less than 1 GB
Data on Critical ChangeLab KPIs	#17	1 GB
Critical ChangeLab Ethics Advisory Board	#18	Less than 1 GB
Critical ChangeLab Expert Advisory Board	#19	Less than 1 GB
Critical ChangeLab Youth Assembly	#20	Less than 1 GB

2.4 Data utility

Table 10. Utility of Critical ChangeLab datasets

Name of the dataset	Dataset code	Group of stakeholders	Utility
Survey data on education institutions' democracy health	#1	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, Formal and non-formal education professionals, Policy and decision-makers	(i) Feed the development of the Democracy Health Index (D1.1) (ii) report on everyday democracy in formal and non-formal education institutions (D1.2) (iii) policy brief (D4.2)
Case studies on youth perspectives on everyday democracy	#2	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners,	Feed the development of (i) report on youth perspectives on everyday democracy (D1.3)

			(ii) policy brief (D4.2)
Secondary research on critical literacies	#3	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, Researchers and research institutions	Feed the development of Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy (D1.4)
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 1)	#4	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Feed the development of Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy (D1.4)
Data stemming from the community of practice building activities	#5	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Implementation of Critical ChangeLab PAR cycles
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 2)	#6	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Feed project report D2.1 and the development of Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy (D3.2)
Documentation of Critical ChangeLabs (PAR cycle 3)	#7	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Feed project report D2.2 and the development of Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy (D3.2)
Documentation of ready-to-go activities and strategies to facilitate Critical ChangeLabs	#8	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, Formal and non-formal education professionals	Feed the development of Critical ChangeLab Educator's Handbook (D2.3)
Critical ChangeLabs process evaluation	#9	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Project evaluation: Feed development of (i) project report D3.1 (ii) policy report (D4.5)
Critical ChangeLab impact evaluation	#10	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Project evaluation: Feed development of (i) project report D3.3 (ii) policy report (D4.5)
Critical ChangeLab socio-economic evaluation	#11	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Project evaluation: Feed development of policy report (D3.4)
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	#12	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners	Monitoring of the progress of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project
Voices of Youth	#13	All Critical ChangeLab stakeholder groups	Dissemination of project results Feed development of young leaders video campaign (D4.4)
Data stemming from dissemination events and activities	#14	All Critical ChangeLab stakeholder groups	Dissemination of project results
Documentation of roundtables and online workshops	#15	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, European Commission (EC) makers	Feed development of policy report (D4.6)
Data on internal project coordination activities	#16	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, EC	Project monitoring and evaluation
Data on Critical ChangeLab KPIs	#17	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, EC	Project monitoring and evaluation

Critical ChangeLab Ethics Advisory Board	#18	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, EC	Project monitoring and evaluation
Critical ChangeLab Expert Advisory Board	#19	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, EC	Project monitoring and feedback
Critical ChangeLab Youth Assembly	#20	Critical ChangeLab consortium partners, EC	Project monitoring and feedback

3 FAIR DATA

The term FAIR, findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, was launched at the "Jointly designing a data FAIRPORT" workshop organized in Lorentz Center, Leiden, Netherlands on 2014. The resulting FAIR guiding principles, published in 2016 by Wilkinson M. D. et al. were adopted by the EC in the form of a guidelines for H2020 research data management (EC, 2016). These guidelines are also maintained in Horizon Europe where beneficiaries are requested to comply with FAIR principles when managing the digital research data generated in EC funded projects.

The FAIR principles as described by the GO FAIR Initiative⁹ are:

- **Findable:** The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, thus, this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.
- **Accessible:** Once a user finds the required data, she/he needs to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.
- **Interoperable:** The data usually have to be integrated with the other data. In addition, the data have to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.
- **Reusable:** The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described, so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All the data that will be produced within the framework of the Critical ChangeLab project will be discoverable with metadata. For this, descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata will be created using metadata standards such as the Dublin Core terms formulated by the Dublin Core™ Metadata Initiative¹⁰, the Data Documentation Initiative¹¹ (DDI), as well as other metadata standards based on the repository where the dataset will be published (Critical ChangeLab basic metadata template is included in Annex 1).

⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/go-fair-initiative/>

¹⁰ <https://www.dublincore.org>

¹¹ <https://ddialliance.org/>

Critical ChangeLab (meta)data and other research outputs will be assigned Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or a handle for all author(s) involved in the action (such as ORCIDs or ResearcherIDs), and made open through a trusted digital repository, as well as indexed in a searchable resource. The Critical ChangeLab research (meta)data will be accessed through the following repositories:

- The Critical ChangeLab website (with links on/to the Social Media profiles).
- Individual Partner websites and the social media groups they are part of.
- The portals of the academic publishers where scientific publications will be accepted.
- Other official sources such as OpenAIRE/Zenodo, Trusted repositories will be selected based on the guidelines of OpenAIRE.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

Critical ChangeLab consortium strongly believes in the transparency of the scientific process, committing to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", and considering sound data management as an essential part of research best practice. In this context Critical ChangeLab will open the project's data that can be useful to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed to the collection/generation of this data. The legal basis for the processing of personal data in Critical ChangeLab is informed consent and thus, opening datasets containing personal identifiers will require authorisation from the data subjects.

When personal data are involved, under General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679, anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques will be applied before the datasets are shared among partners or made public. The OpenAIRE's Amnesia¹² data anonymisation tool will also be an additional asset to be used if necessary. All personal data collected/generated will be considered as closed data prior to their anonymisation. The availability of the data will be ensured by utilizing trusted research data repositories such as Zenodo,, along with relevant documentation and linked metadata for each dataset.

All data will be licensed under Creative Commons licenses (see Section 3.4), thus making it openly available to everyone interested.

In general, if confidentiality, security, personal data protection obligations or IPR issues forbid open access to certain data produced by the project, it will be deposited in a

¹² <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

restricted repository, and access may be granted upon request and under the conditions of a restricted license. Such data produced by the project cannot be released as open data and is presented within the chapter “Purpose of data collection or/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project” together with an explanation of the reasons that prohibit open access.

It is expected that the Critical ChangeLab open data will be easily accessible without the need to use a specialised method, software tool and/or documentation. Anyone interested in accessing Critical ChangeLab’s open data will be able to simply use a web browser (e.g. Firefox, Chrome, Edge, Safari, etc.) to access Zenodo’s website . By default, Zenodo supports file uploads up 50GB (= 50.000 MB) and max 100 files. Via the Zenodo search engine a user can simply type the name of the Critical ChangeLab project (or any other relevant keyword connected to the Critical ChangeLab data) to be directed to the project’s open data, available for re-use. Closed data will only be accessible by the authorised project partners through the usage of a regularly back-upped encrypted network drive.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The Critical ChangeLab consortium aims to make the project’s datasets accessible and interoperable as much as possible. Thus, it will seek compliance with various standards, such as the Open Definition¹³ of the Open Knowledge International¹⁴, and will follow the best practices and guidelines for working with open data such as the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive Managers 2.0¹⁵.

Metadata files will be created and linked with each dataset to facilitate their discoverability and usability over time. An example of a metadata template can be found in Annex A. Common data formats will be used to make data easily integrated with other data, applications, and workflows. The majority of data will be available in spreadsheets (.xls), text (.docx) and similar formats. All (meta)data published in repositories will follow a uniform naming standard.

¹³ <https://opendefinition.org/>

¹⁴ <https://okfn.org/en/>

¹⁵ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>

3.4 Increase data re-use

Critical ChangeLab will utilize the Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0)¹⁶ license for the (meta)data that is generated throughout the project duration. Software and tools will be also open source with Creative Commons licenses. The Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike license allows to re-distribute and re-use a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited and that any derivative work is made available under “the same, similar or a compatible license”. This type of license is widely used and generally considered as a “best practice” by a broad spectrum of projects and actors within the domains of open research data and conforms to the Open Definition requirements of reusability and compatibility.

Critical ChangeLab aims to document its research data in a way that ensures it can be interpreted, shared and reused by the scientific community. The raw data will be preserved on partners’ infrastructure. Whenever possible, raw data will be anonymised or at least pseudonymised by removing unique personal identifiers such as names. Once pseudonymised/anonymised, the raw data will be deleted provided it is not necessary for research purposes. The processed data (pseudonymised/anonymised) will be retained as long as it is useful for the research purposes it has been collected.

Any open data collected will be publicly available by the end of the respective Work Package functioning, and the public deliverables will be available online through the project website. Before uploading, data profiling and data cleansing (where applicable) activities such as outlier removal and missing data interpolation will take place to assure the quality of the data.

¹⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 Cost estimation for making data FAIR

There will be no extra costs involved for making data FAIR, as costs related to support findability, access, interoperability and reusability have already been included in the project's proposal and has already been taken into account when calculating and distributing effort among the project's partners.

Since all collected (meta)data will be uploaded to the Zenodo data repository as well as national research data repositories in line with the European Commission Data Deposit Policy, a long-term preservation of all data is ensured without any additional costs even after the project's completion.

4.2 Data management responsibilities

Specific data management roles are established to ensure the effective, proper and secure handling of the Critical ChangeLab data, as agreed in the Critical ChangeLab Consortium Agreement.

Each partner is responsible for the processing of its data and others will not have any access to it (unless completely anonymised). Regarding personal data processing, all partners of the project act as Joint Controllers of the data since they co-define together the purposes and means of the processing (Art. 26 GDPR).

In general, the project coordinator (UOULU) will be the overall responsible for the data management within the scope of the Critical ChangeLab project and will coordinate together with Work Package and Task Leaders the collection and storage of all data during the project's lifetime, as well as which data and how it will be open for re-use. In addition, UOULU is responsible for supervising the implementation of the project in terms of GDPR at the project scale. UOULU is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary, along with support of all partners).

Task leaders of research tasks involving personal data collection are responsible for producing data de-identification/anonymization plans for the specific tasks. Task leaders of research tasks are responsible for producing a plan as to which data and how it will be open for re-use, using a template such as the one included in Annex 1. Task leaders of

research tasks are responsible for arranging a training session for the partners In these tasks.

Each partner is locally responsible for the local collection, anonymisation and safe storage of its data. Each partner is responsible for opening its data for re-use, communicating of this process to project coordinators and partners to give them an opportunity to review and raise any issues, as well as uploading the data to the Zenodo repository afterwards.

During its second reporting period, the Critical ChangeLab project implemented the following procedure of data management.

Figure 1. Critical ChangeLab Data Management procedure

5 Data security

The Critical ChangeLab project pays special attention to data security and especially the protection of personal and sensitive data. Thus, the consortium aims to ensure that appropriate procedures, protocols and technologies to be applied to safeguard any data breach, accidental loss and/or unauthorized manipulation.

The personal and sensitive data within Critical ChangeLab will be closed until their anonymisation. During and upon collection, these data will be stored on the partners' servers and they should be backed up regularly. Each partner will be responsible for data security when data is transmitted and stored under their premises. This includes an obligation to store them under restricted and secure access, to prevent unwarranted disclosure to third parties even within the same organization, to maintain the highest reasonable standard of protection and accountability, and lastly to report without undue delay to the coordinator, the national data protection authorities and the affected data subjects any data loss or breach.

The closed data will be accessible only to the authorized partners. In addition, partners must ensure that the form of any publication, including publication on the Internet, neither directly nor indirectly leads to a breach of agreed confidentiality and anonymity.

To increase data security partners consider destruction of the raw personal and sensitive data (depending on the type of collection – see 'Data Summary' part) and keep only the anonymised data for the needs of the research activities. In that case, the current version of the Data Management plan will be updated accordingly.

Moreover, privacy policies will be developed to define how the Critical ChangeLab website and platform will be processing and using personal data, which security procedures will be followed and what cookies policy will be employed as well as describe the users' rights (see Annex 2)

6 Ethical aspects

The Critical ChangeLab project activities include collection of personal and sensitive data from the target groups of the project. To ensure compliance with all GDPR rules and that no ethical issues will be raised, Critical ChangeLab project will develop appropriate informed consent procedures as well as a personal data protection processes (this will be specified in D6.3 OEI - Requirement No. 3).

The Critical ChangeLab team is committed to protecting and safeguarding the physical and psychological integrity of the participants in the project when performing their research work and in the context of their regular activities.

Any data processing activities within the project will be carried out in accordance with the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (in particular articles 7 and 8), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, and the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 as well as applicable national data protection legislation and other applicable laws.

In line with the above-mentioned regulations and best practices for research integrity and ethics, the following Ethical and GDPR principles should be applied to all Critical ChangeLab data collection actions that involve personal data:

1. Critical ChangeLab partners process personal data only for the purposes defined between the partners, they guarantee the confidentiality of the data covered by the Grant Agreement (GA) and implement all appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect personal data communicated to it or recorded in the course of the project against accidental or unlawful destruction or accidental loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure or access, including in connection with the transmission of data over a network, and against all other unlawful forms of processing.
2. Personal data processing risk assessment will be conducted to assess the risks relating to the processing of personal data. If necessary, data impact assessments might be also conducted before data collection activities involving personal data take place.
3. Data subjects must always be informed for which purpose and how the project/partner will process their personal data, the legal basis for the processing (public interest or consent), and their rights under the GDPR and the national law.

Data subjects should be informed in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.

4. Data subjects should be informed about any disclosures and transfers of data.
5. When the project cannot contact the data subjects, an information sheet (privacy note) must be published.
6. Critical ChangeLab partners have to make sure to do not exacerbate people's vulnerability through the research or research participation.

Critical ChangeLab has also appointed and works in collaboration with an independent Ethics Advisory Board (AB) (information about the members of the Ethics AB and their roles and functions within the project are detailed in D6.1). The Ethics AB members' experience helps the Critical ChangeLab consortium to assess the issues along the entire project duration and to check for compliance with ethical standards and related legislation for the protection of personal data. To M6 of the project, Ethics advisors' advice and recommendations were namely sought during the identification of national requirements and regulations regarding data collection activities. Critical ChangeLab coordinators will continue regular communication with the Ethics AB to consult them on aspects related to the preparation of the data collection methodology, tools and consents necessary for the conduction of Critical ChangeLab activities, as well as the data processing procedures.

Within the consortium, the data collection methodology, processing procedures, tools and consents necessary for the development of Critical ChangeLab research and innovation activities will be reviewed and validated by the DPOs of partners who implement these actions, as well as by TCD, UB and ISRZ research ethics committees.

7 Conclusions and next steps

The current document constitutes the second version of the Critical ChangeLab Data Management Plan. The generated project's datasets, their metadata definitions and the followed standards and guidelines for curating, sharing and preserving these data have been defined in line with the project's requirements, the consortium's expertise and the relevant procedures described in the FAIR Data Management guidelines (EC, 2016).

The types of the Critical ChangeLab research data have been defined, including open and closed data. Data processing pipelines and methodologies have been established. Some of the data to be collected or generated will be openly available as FAIR data, using interoperable data formats and published under Creative Commons licenses, facilitating reuse and generation of a robust evidence base for democratic curriculum development. Such open data is one of the sustainable results of the project and will be deposited for long term preservation in the Zenodo research data repository.

The Critical ChangeLab Data Management Plan is a "living" document to be updated during the project as the research activities evolve to include new data, adjustments in the processes deployed, changes in consortium policies or any other issue regarding the data management of the project.

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Annexes

ANNEX 1

Critical ChangeLab Metadata File Template

#	Element	Meaning
1	Title	The name given the resource
2	Creator	The person or organization responsible for the content
3	Subject	The topic covered
4	Description	A textual outline of the content
5	Publisher	Those responsible for making the resource available
6	Contributor	Those who added to the content
7	Date	When the resource was made available
8	Type	A category for the content
9	Format	How the resource is presented
10	Identifier	Numerical identifier for the content, such as a URL
11	Source	From where the content originally derived
12	Language	In what language the content is written
13	Relation	How the content relates to other resources
14	Coverage	Where the resource is physically located
15	Rights	A link to a copyright notice

ANNEX 2

Critical ChangeLab Website Data Protection Statement

In Compliance with Our Duty to Inform You

Protecting your personal data is a top priority for us. Accordingly, we process your data in strict compliance with legal regulations (DSGVO, DSG, TKG 2003). This Data Protection Declaration provides you with information about the most important aspects of data processing in conjunction with our website.

Information disclosed in accordance with Art. 13 GDPR

In case personal data relating to a data subject are collected from the data subject, Ars Electronica Linz GmbH & Co KG (hereinafter AE) will comply with its obligations according to Art. 13 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as follows:

1. The party responsible for processing data is Ars Electronica Linz GmbH & Co KG, Ars-Electronica-Straße 1, 4040 Linz, Austria; telephone: +43 732 7272 0; e-mail: dsk@ars.electronica.art
2. Data are processed for the following purposes:
 - 2.1. Transacting business with clients and associates of AE, possibly in the pre-contractual stage of the relationship
 - 2.2. Doing promotional work in various media to publicize AE's activities
 - 2.3. Managing the subscriber list of AE's newsletter
 - 2.4. Organizing events
 - 2.5. Administering AE's website: Newsletter subscribers' data will not be transferred to third parties. Every newsletter will be sent in such a way that no recipient receives information about other recipients. The use of data for the purpose of the newsletter (including the mail server employed for the newsletter's distribution) is hosted on EDP infrastructure of eworx Network & Internet GmbH (agent commissioned by AE).Data employed to administer

the website will be transferred to a third party only if an attack or illegal access is presumed to have occurred; then, data will be transferred to technical experts and law enforcement agencies solely for the purpose of ascertaining the identity of and prosecuting the perpetrator.

3. Data will not be transferred to third parties in foreign countries or to international organizations.
4. The deadlines for the deletion of data are derived from the legally mandated terms for the storage of such data.
5. There exists a right of access by the data subject according to Art. 15 GDPR, a right to rectification according to Art. 16 GDPR, a right to erasure (right to be forgotten) according to Art. 17 GDPR, a right to restriction of processing according to Art. 18 GDPR, a right to data portability according to Art. 20 GDPR, and a right to object to processing according to Art. 21 GDPR.
6. A complaint may be filed with the Austrian Data Protection Authority (www.data-protection-authority.gv.at).
7. No automated individual decision-making occurs.
8. Data will not be used subsequently for any other purpose.

Information disclosed in accordance with Art. 14 GDPR

In case personal data have not been obtained from the data subject, the following information will be provided:

1. The party responsible for processing data is Ars Electronica Linz GmbH & Co KG, Ars-Electronica-Straße 1, 4040 Linz, Austria; telephone: +43 732 7272 0, e-mail: dsk@ars.electronica.art
2. Data are processed for the following purposes:
 - 2.1. Transacting business with clients and associates of AE, possibly in the pre-contractual stage of the relationship
 - 2.2. Doing promotional work in various media to publicize AE's activities
 - 2.3 Organizing events

- 2.4. Administering AE's website
3. The following categories of data are processed:
 - 3.1. Data of contact persons on the staff of clients & associates: name, function, e-mail address, address, telephone & FAX numbers
 - 3.2. Data of media outlet representatives: name, function, e-mail address, address, telephone & FAX numbers
 - 3.3. Organization of events, provided that the data is not registered in connection with each participant individually: name, address, e-mail address, address, telephone & FAX numbers (if necessary), reason for the invitation, accepted/declined
 - 3.4. Administering AE's website: IP address, pages visited, date & time info, indications of attacks or illegal access Newsletter subscribers' data will not be transferred to third parties. Every newsletter will be sent in such a way that no recipient receives information about other recipients. The use of data for the purpose of the newsletter (including the mail server employed for the newsletter's distribution) is hosted on EDP infrastructure of eworx Network & Internet GmbH (agent commissioned by AE). Data employed to administer the website will be transferred to a third party only if an attack or illegal access is presumed to have occurred; then, data will be transferred to technical experts and law enforcement agencies solely for the purpose of ascertaining the identity of and prosecuting the perpetrator.
4. Data will not be transferred to third parties in foreign countries or to international organizations.
5. The deadlines for the deletion of data are derived from the legally mandated terms for the storage of such data.
6. There exists a right of access by the data subject according to Art. 15 GDPR, a right to rectification according to Art. 16 GDPR, a right to erasure (right to be forgotten) according to Art. 17 GDPR, a right to restriction of processing according to Art. 18 GDPR, a right to data portability according to Art. 20 GDPR, and a right to object to processing according to Art. 21 GDPR.
7. A complaint may be filed with the Austrian Data Protection Authority (www.data-protection-authority.gv.at).

8. No automated individual decision-making occurs.
9. Data will not be used subsequently for any other purpose.

Contact with Us

If you contact us via a form on our website or via e-mail, then the data you input will be stored to memory for up to six months in order to process your query and, if need be, to reply to follow-up queries. These data will not be divulged to others without your consent.

Cookies

Our website uses so-called cookies, small packets of information that are deposited on your device with the help of your browser. We use cookies in order to make our offerings more user-friendly. Some cookies remain stored to memory on your device until you delete them. They enable us to recognize your browser the next time you visit our website. If you have reservations about receiving cookies, then you can set your browser to inform you of a cookie being sent to you, so that you can accept or reject it, as you wish. Deactivating cookies can impair the performance of our website's features.

Web Analysis

Our website uses functions of the MATOMO web analytics application. All data are immediately pseudonymized and saved to memory on our servers. These data are not personalized; thus, it's impossible for us to ascertain which user accessed what data. These data are not transferred to third (non-European) countries. You can prevent this by setting your browser to not save cookies. The data processing is done in compliance with the legal provisions of '§ 96 Abs 3 TKG and of Art 6 Abs 1 lit a (Consent) and/or f (Legitimate Interest) of the DSGVO. Our matter of concern in the context of the DSGVO (Legitimate Interest) is to optimize our offerings and our online presence. We respect your Do Not Track settings.

Newsletter

You have the option of subscribing to our newsletter via our website. To do so, we need your e-mail address and your declaration of consent to receiving our newsletter. In order to deliver targeted information to you, we also gather and process information you voluntarily provide about your areas of interest, title, institution, street, postal/Zip code, city and country. As soon as you register to receive our newsletter, we send you an e-mail containing a link to confirm your registration. You can cancel your newsletter subscription at any time. To do

so, click on the Unsubscribe link to be found in any issue of the newsletter and follow your browser's instructions. Or, if you wish, you can cancel by sending an e-mail to info@ars.electronica.art. We will then immediately delete any data gathered in conjunction with your newsletter subscription.

Video Surveillance

Certain limited and clearly designated areas of Ars Electronica's business premises are under video surveillance. This measure is for the organization's own protection (safeguarding the property of the organization and of its employees), for the purpose carrying out its corporate responsibilities (e.g. to provide for traffic safety and in compliance with contractual provisions with respect to its customers), as well as for the purpose of prevention, containment and prosecution of criminally relevant conduct to the extent that this is within Ars Electronica's legal purview. Video surveillance recordings are screened and evaluated only in connection with incidents related to the above-mentioned purposes. The legal basis for making these video recordings is Ars Electronica's legitimate interest in protecting its property and complying with its legal obligations. Generally, data are stored for 72 hours; in the case of an incident, for the duration of the legal proceedings that result from it.

While these surveillance videos are being shot, the location and time-of-day of the recordings, the image data, the identity (if distinguishable) and role of the persons whose images were captured (e.g. perpetrator, witness, victim) are registered and processed. The data will not be forwarded to recipients who use this data for their own benefit. Provided that there is a corresponding legal obligation to do so, the data will, at most, be provided to government agencies and/or courts with jurisdiction over the particular matter (to obtain evidence in criminal or civil proceedings), public safety agencies (for policing purposes), witnesses, victims (in conjunction with the assertion of their claims), insurers (solely for the purpose of processing insurance claims), attorneys, government agencies and other authorities for the purpose of law enforcement.

There is no provision for turning over this data to recipients in a third country or to an international organization. No automated decision-making (profiling) is done. Making data available to the individuals captured on such videos is neither contractually nor legally mandatory, and there is also no obligation to do so. We draw your attention to the fact that there exists no right to data portability.

Photo and video recording

We make photos and videos at events and exhibitions. These are published for the presentation of our activities on our website and also in social media channels as well as in print media, in particular also catalogues, daily newspapers, folders, brochures and other advertising media or become part of our online archive.

Exhibition installations

In the case of several of the exhibited installations, which are marked with a separate reference, photographs and/or video recordings are made, sometimes randomly and without any further action by a person, and presented to interested visitors as part of the installations. This is done for artistic and educational purposes.

Your Rights

You have the following basic rights: information, correction, deletion, restriction, data portability, revocation, and objection. To exercise these rights, please click here: dsk@ars.electronica.art.

If you believe that processing your data violates your right to data protection, or that your entitlement to data protection has been violated in some other way, you can contact the appropriate federal regulatory agency. In Austria, this is the [Datenschutzbehörde](#) [data protection authority].

How to contact us:

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